

Quality Inspection of Battery Separators by Partial Discharge Spectroscopy

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Quality control is highly relevant for safety, sustainability and efficiency of the battery manufacturing process. An early and reliable detection of failures in the production chain is important. Here we present a method for detecting micrometric imperfections and contaminations on the battery separator before filling the battery stack with the electrolyte. We sense these irregularities by measuring an increase of partial discharges when applying between the battery electrodes potentials close, but still well below the breakdown voltage of the separator. We can distinguish different degrees and different types of contamination with a very high confidence. This is

enabled by a throughout statistical analysis of the partial discharge events. The overall reliability of detecting a contaminated against the clean separator is 96%. The technique, as implemented here, uses categorization procedures and machine learning algorithms to automate decision-making and can accelerate the quality assessment process in pilot lines or small-manufacturing. Compared to other methods, like optical detection or full discharge measurements, the here presented approach is very reliable, simple to implement and virtually noninvasive.

Introduction

The increasing performance of rechargeable battery technologies is considered a prime factor for the development of new mobile technologies in a variety of different fields.^[1] Among various battery chemistry, Lithium ions have become the most popular choice for battery-powered applications^[2] due to their high energy and power densities.^[3] The canvas of battery applications covers low power, mobile devices in households and for personal use,^[4] as well high-power applications like electric vehicles and other industrial applications.^[5]

To guarantee the reliability and operational safety of current and upcoming battery technologies and increase the sustainability of the production process, quality gates at each production step of the battery are required. One of the important factors is the quality of the separator membrane, which physically separates the cathode and anode while allowing the diffusion of ions between the electrodes. The separator thickness should be minimal to achieve higher conductivity for a cell but avoid any risk of touching electrodes. A direct ohmic contact between both electrodes would lead to

a high local current and could cause a thermal runaway of the battery cell. Therefore, a quality check of the separator membrane is of high priority in a production line.^[6] Besides an optical check of the exact placement of the separator between the electrodes,^[7] it consists of detection of particle contamination and search of a void location on the membrane surface. Conducting particles (e.g. from the electrodes themselves or the current collectors etc.) pose an especially high risk since they can short-circuit the electrodes or lead to high local electric fields.^[8] Existing techniques for examination of such contaminations can include optical imaging of separator surfaces,^[9,10] or electrical techniques.^[13] Optical imaging techniques are expensive and time-consuming and cannot be used when the cells are assembled, because of the missing optical access.^[11] In our previous work, we introduced a high-voltage electrical discharge measurement method to examine separator integrity.^[14,17] However, since this method operates very close to the breakdown voltage of the separator material and relies on the detection of a single discharge event, the detection reliability of contaminated separators was limited. Also, false positive contaminations were detected, pointing to the fact that the full discharge method is not non-invasive.^[12] The here presented technique is fully non-invasive, more reliable, and faster, since it requires lower voltages and is based on the detection of a large number of statistically distributed partial discharge events. The highest voltage that is typically applied across the electrodes is between 350 V and 400 V, rather than between 450 V and 500 V as in full discharge methods. The paper is built up in the following way: the first section will give insight into the measurement setup and describe the measurement and analysis methodology in general. In the results section, we prove the reliability of the technique for classifying different types and degrees of contamination.

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Methodology and Development of the Technique

High-voltage discharge phenomena are well-studied in the literature^[16] since they are typically destructive and have to be avoided by appropriate design in high-voltage grids, transformers, etc. Besides the full electric discharge that is caused by an electrical breakdown of the entire insulating material between two electrodes at a characteristic breakdown voltage, partial discharge (PD) events occur already below this voltage. They are associated with local discharges happening stochastically in the material where the local electric field strength is increased and can be measured as short current spikes. In contrast to full discharges, they are typically non-destructive. While in gasses and simple electrode configurations, the partial discharge process can be described analytically by an inception condition derived from plasma physics equations, the prediction of partial discharge in more complex structures and materials is more difficult, since it depends on the local microscopic material properties of the insulator material and the electrodes.^[7] However, a sharply protruding conductive particle causes a localized increase in electric field on a qualitative level. In addition to the particles' microscopic shape, it also depends on its material properties, specifically its conductivity.^[14]

Exactly this sensitivity to local changes in the material properties is what we exploit in our method to spot local

contaminations or any irregularities in the separator material by measuring the local discharge events. These events are observed as spikes of current in the range of a few hundred nA and can be observed after applying the voltage across the electrodes. The more contaminated the separator is, the more often we observe discharges exhibiting also higher peak currents.

An electrical schematic of the measurement setup with a conceptual sketch of the cell structure including two metallic electrodes containing a dielectric separator in between is shown in Figure 1a. The electrodes are conductive enough to form equipotential planes after the application of voltage, V , and allow for the detection of discharge events.

Measurement of such events requires a sensitive current meter capable of resolving currents in the range of one to a few hundreds of nA as shown in Figure 1b. At these current levels external noise will be a prime factor of interference for measurements which urges a noise prevention shielding. A chamber in a suitable shape to place the electrodes is carved into a square shape piece of Teflon. The thickness of square shape Teflon piece is 2.5 cm. The chamber containing the cell structure is shielded by a metallic casing, which reduces external noise to less than 2 nA. Connections are done using low-noise coaxial cables with BNC connectors. Current spikes can only be read entirely if a current meter can provide a high enough bandwidth as these occur very frequent in time intervals. A current waveform analyzer with a bandwidth up to 10 MHz is used in our experiments which ensures the collection

Figure 1. Measurement set up for partial discharge measurements. a) Sketch of the measurement setup and circuit diagram. Keysight B2985 A is used as a high voltage source (photos and equipment courtesy of Keysight Technologies, USA). Keysight CX3324 A is used for recording fast-occurring partial discharge events. A custom-shielded fixture is used to place the separator between electrodes and do the measurements. b) Typical current signal acquired with the current waveform analyzer.

of all current spikes within an observation time. Moreover, a high-voltage source with

low output noise is required (we use Keysight B2985 A). The voltage source contains a 20 M Ω resistor that limits the current limiting to a safe level. Coaxial cables specified for high-voltage and very low noise values connect the high-voltage source and current waveform analyzer to the electrodes via BNC connectors. BNC connection provides rigidity of connection, prevents undesired signal losses and at the same time ensures the perfect grounding of the shielded fixture.

For the measurement the electrodes containing the separator sample are placed inside the chamber, which is enclosed in a metal shielding case. Application of voltage across the electrodes causes partial discharges, which are acquired with high bandwidth by the current meter.

The measurement data shown in Figure 1b represents the typical current signal over a sampling time of 12 s exhibiting partial discharges on a highly contaminated separator sample. As can be seen, the current spikes reach values up to 150 nA, well above the system noise level which is in the range of 2 to 5 nA.

Results and Discussion

To characterize the reliability of the developed partial discharge technique for spotting contaminations on battery separators, we compare the following the current noise induced by partial discharge under different experimental conditions and for different degrees and types of contamination. Finally, we derive a scheme that allows us to classify separator contamination based on the specific noise figure measured with our method.

Sample Preparation

Commercially available separator samples (FS3011 22 samples, Freudenberg Performance Material, Germany) consisting of proprietary polymer membrane, coated with ceramic materials, with a thickness of 22 μm are used for all the measurements. The dimensions of the anode and cathode are 50 \times 70 mm and 45.5 \times 65 mm in BLB1 configuration, respectively. Measurements were performed in air, at a constant temperature of 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and relative humidity of 20–30%. Contaminant particles of different materials are gently placed on the separator surface in different quantities. Contaminating particles are originating from the same Lithium Nickel Manganese Cobalt Oxide (NMC622) electrode, graphite electrode and a metallic current collector. The average particle size varies from 12 μm –100 μm . There are three levels of contamination: low contamination (10–15 particles), Moderate contamination (20–30 particles), and high contamination (30–50 particles).

Data Acquisition and Treatment

The separator-electrode samples are placed into the fixture (Figure 2a and Figure S2) and an increasing DC voltage is applied in steps from 200 V to 400 V, resulting in an average electric field in the separator of $E=U/d \sim 10\text{--}20 \text{ V}/\mu\text{m}$. Each voltage step is applied for a fixed length of time. The current waveform analyzer is set to data logger mode and measurement parameters like duration of waveform recording, sampling rate are set. In the here reported measurements, we used a rate of waveform recording of 500 kHz for a time length of 10–40 s for each voltage step i.e., 3.2 min total time length for one full measurement. A high sampling rate allows us to capture a high amount of the dynamics of the partial discharge events and delivers a large amount of PD data for statistical analysis. However, for high throughput measurements, the sampling time can be reduced by one order of magnitude if the value of the current limiting resistor is reduced. For the used separators voltages above 300 V–350 V lead to a statistically relevant number of partial discharges, if any contamination is present on the separator surface. These partial discharges are in the range of 20 nA–200 nA and are acquired in the data logger mode of the current waveform analyzer.

The stepwise increase of the voltage, which we call the preconditioning step, is on the one hand important since it removes static charges sometimes present in the electrode separator stack after assembly and would sometimes lead to a full discharge current spike. On the other hand, the voltage dependency of the partial discharges allows us to distinguish between different contamination types, as we will discuss later.

Partial Discharge Noise Spectroscopy

For the here used separator material, optimal measurement conditions with a high number of partial discharges and almost no full discharges were achieved at a final voltage of 400 V. Figure S1 shows the current versus time traces for the three different degrees of contamination on the separator material.

As can be seen in Figure S1, even for the clean separator some partial discharges can be observed in the signal (green line). The number of PDs increases with contamination on the sample surface (orange and magenta lines). This is due to the high conductivity and rough shape of the particles that locally increase the electrical field at the electrode separator interface. A higher number of particles present on the surface of a separator sample leads to more partial discharge events. Interestingly, the power spectrum in Figure 2b shows an increase in the noise power spectrum at frequencies below 140 kHz. We associate this with the source noise of the high-voltage source. Only at 150 kHz, we can clearly distinguish between the partial discharge noise spectrum of clean, little, fully contaminated separator. The difference in contamination can be measured by a >10 dB difference in the noise power. We note also that a bandwidth of 500 kHz is sufficient to segregate the different contaminations.

Figure 2. Partial discharge current time traces analysed statistically and spectrally. a) Partial discharge current spikes are visualized, and current peak height and dwell time duration between constitutive spikes are indicated. b) Power spectrum of partial discharge current events for both moderate and high contamination levels, partial discharge events are recorded at a sample rate of 500 kS/s. c) Histogram displaying the partial discharge dwell time distribution against current for clean separator and two distinct contamination levels (moderate and high). The absolute number of counts is displayed. The same data integrated in the horizontal and vertical directions are displayed in the side and bottom histograms, respectively.

Statistical Data Analysis

While the noise spectrum in Figure 2b allows already to distinguish between different amounts of contamination, a statistical analysis of these partial discharge events reveals more information on the type and degree of contamination.

As can be seen from Figure 2a the peak value of a partial discharge event and dwell time are the two important parameters to discuss. On the contaminated samples the partial discharge current reaches peak values of up to 100 nA and the dwell time between constitutive current spikes is as low as 0.2 ms. For the clean sample, only a few partial discharge spikes with very low peak values are observed during the time trace visualized in Figure 2a.

A statistical visualization of these parameters on the entire data set is shown in Figure 2c. The distribution of the dwell times between partial discharge events is plotted against the current peak height distribution. The plot shows that the dwell time maximum is reduced for a clean separator from 40 ms to 25 ms as the contamination level increases. With this also the number of discharge events increases as the contamination increases. A clean sample under observation shows the maximum counts for low dwell time values in the case of a highly contaminated sample. The bottom histogram in Figure 2c depicts that a greater number of peaks i.e., the maximum value of 100 counts is observed for highly contaminated samples. As the contamination level reduces also the number of partial discharge events does. Figure 2c) shows the

minimum dwell time of 0.12 ms is observed for the highest contaminated sample, which means as contamination increases, the occurrence of current peaks with higher current values is measured. The highest value of a current peak is observed as 200 nA.

Quantification of Separator Contamination

In the previous section, we have shown that contaminations on the separator lead to a characteristic change in the statistical distribution of partial discharges.

To show the reliability of the method, we repeated measurements on 3 samples with identical contamination levels and two times on the same sample. To assess the sensitivity separator samples with 3 degrees of contamination of carbon particles were measured. Representative distribution of dwell time and peak current is shown in the main Figures 3 a–c for a clean, moderately, and strongly contaminated separator together with the optical image of the contamination on the separator before full assembly in the respective insets. For the clean sample a maximum value of discharge current is observed as 20 nA and the dwell time ceiling is at $t_{d, \text{clean}} = 60$ ms. The highest number of partial discharge peaks are observed with a current value of $i_{p, \text{clean}} = 15\text{--}18$ nA. With increasing contamination (c1 and c2 refer to low and high contamination, respectively), the peak current increases to $i_{p, c1} = 50$ nA and $i_{p, c2} = 60$ nA, respec-

Figure 3. Classification of separators by dwell time, peak current, and discharge counts. a–c) The typical count distribution of the discharge current peak value and dwell time is shown for the three respective degrees of contamination as indicated in each figure (The normalized number of counts is shown by the colour scale). d) The maximum value of peak discharge current versus the maximum dwell time is shown for the data from a)–c). The additional points mark the repetition of the measurements as discussed in the text. Note, that the size of the circle denotes the count number. The measurement voltage was 400 V.

tively, while the maximum dwell time drops to $t_{d,c1} = 30$ ms, and $t_{d,c2} = 45$ ms, respectively.

To classify the amount of contamination in a separator we use these two parameters together with the absolute count number of partial discharges. As can be seen in Figure 3d there is a clear and statistically relevant difference between the three values for clean contaminated separators: clean separator's have typically low discharge currents, low number of counts, and high dwell times. Highly contaminated separators show generally the opposite behavior, however, there is the relevant spread of the discharge current throughout the strongly contaminated samples. The moderately contaminated sample separators show an intermediate response. It is important to notice that the differently contaminated samples are generally located at different positions throughout the dwell time versus the current graph. Only for one out of 24 measurements the clean and moderately contaminated samples overlap, however, the number of counts still differs significantly.

Based on this we can classify the separators using the numerical classification method "Logistic regression" implemented in Mathematica.^[18] We used 50% of the measured data, to teach the classification algorithm and obtained on average an 85% probability for the correct classification of clean

separators and 68% of contaminated separators using the remaining test data. Considering the relatively small amount of available data for teaching the classification algorithm we expect still a clear improvement of the procedure when more data is available. However already, with the available data the separation between contaminated and uncontaminated separators was possible in virtually every case (96% correct classification). This means our method and the analysis allow for almost perfect recognition of faulty separator samples.

Quantification of Contamination Type

Finally, we investigated the potential use of the technique to distinguish between different types of contamination on the separator. Small amounts of particles from the cathode (NMC), anode (graphite), and from the aluminum current collector were placed on the separator and measured repeatedly as shown in Figure 4. The dwell time versus the current distribution is visualized for the three materials for voltage of 300 V and 400 V. The corresponding classification chart is shown in Figure 4b.

Figure 4. Classification of different types of contamination by partial discharge. a) The typical count distribution of the discharge current peak value and dwell time is shown for 3 types of contamination as indicated in each figure, both for 300 and 400 V applied. d) The maximum value of peak discharge current versus the maximum dwell time is shown for the data from a) for the respective voltages. Note, that the size of the circle denotes the count number.

While the voltage dependency of the noise spectra is expected from the theory, it is interesting to see that the application of lower voltage is slightly favorable to separate different types of particle contamination. Nevertheless, at 300 V graphite particles lead to almost no partial discharges rendering the technique ineffective. Consequently, voltage levels should be adapted according to the separator and type of expected contamination.

Conclusions

In summary, we have demonstrated a new technique for quality assessment of battery electrode separator assemblies in the early production stage that is based on high-voltage partial discharge measurements. The developed technique is highly noninvasive and detects the presence of contamination particles on the separator surface between both electrodes by a sensitive current meter detecting current pulses originating from high-voltage partial discharge events. Based on the statistical distribution of the partial discharge events over time and current it is possible to detect the presence of particle contamination in the separator sheet with more than 96% success rate. Even the type of contamination can be inferred using this statistical data analysis procedure. The decision-making, if the separator is contaminated or not, can be automatized by classification and machine learning algorithms, which makes this procedure ideal for application in the production line or battery pilot line.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords: partial discharge · battery separator · quality control · high voltage · dielectrics

- [1] Y. Liang, C. Z. Zhao, H. Yuan, Y. Chen, W. Zhang, J. Q. Huang, D. Yu, Y. Liu, M. M. Titirici, Y. L. Chueh, H. Yu, 2019. A review of rechargeable batteries for portable electronic devices. *InfoMat*, 1(1), pp.6–32.
[2] Pistoia, G. ed. *Lithium-ion batteries: advances and applications*, 2013, pp. 612.

- [3] J. Li, Z. Du, R. E. Ruther, S. J. An, L. A. David, K. Hays, M. Wood, N. D. Phillip, Y. Sheng, C. Mao, S. Kalnaus, 2017. Toward low-cost, high-energy density, and high-power density lithium-ion batteries. *Jom*, 69(9), pp.1484–1496.
- [4] S. Megahed, W. Ebner, *J. Power Sources* **1995**, 54(1), 155–162.
- [5] A. Masias, J. Marcicki, W. A. Paxton, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2021**, 6(2), 621–630.
- [6] F. Dai, M. Cai, *Communications Materials* **2022**, 3(1), 64.
- [7] R. S. Baldwin, W. R. Bennet, E. K. Wong, M. R. Lewton, M. K. Harris, Battery Separator Characterization and Evaluation Procedures for NASA's Advanced Lithium-Ion Batteries (No. E-17182), **2010**.
- [8] X. Zhang, E. Sahraei, K. Wang, *Sci. Rep.* **2016**, 6(1), 1–9.
- [9] J. Huber, C. Tammer, A. Kempter, C. Seidel, G. Reinhart, Optical quality inspection of battery separators. *Technisches Messen*, **2015**.
- [10] J. Huber, C. Tammer, S. Krotil, S. Waidmann, X. Hao, C. Seidel, G. Reinhart, *Procedia Cirp* **2016**, 57, 585–590.
- [11] Z. Deng, X. Lin, Z. Huang, J. Meng, Y. Zhong, G. Ma, Y. Zhou, Y. Shen, H. Ding, Y. Huang, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2021**, 11(2), 2000806.
- [12] X. Zhang, J. Zhu, E. Sahraei, *RSC Adv.* **2017**, 7(88), 56099–56107.
- [13] M. F. Lagadec, R. Zahn, V. Wood, *Nat. Energy* **2019**, 4(1), 16–25.
- [14] L. Hoffmann, M. Kasper, M. Kahn, G. Gramse, G. Ventura Silva, C. Herrmann, M. Kurrat, F. Kienberger, *Batteries* **2021**, 7(4), 64.
- [15] G. E. Hale, N. Kent, Publications of the Yerkes Observatory, **1907**, 3, 2-i.
- [16] S. Chandrasekar, C. Kalaivanan, G. C. Montanari, A. Cavallini, *Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation* **2010**, 17(1), 181–188.
- [17] R. Leithoff, *Energies MDPI* **2022**, 15(7), 2670.
- [18] Wolfram Mathematica Function Reference. Version 12.2, <https://reference.wolfram.com/language/ref/method/LogisticRegression.html>, accessed 12/2023.

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